

YOGA EDUCATION: PANACEA FOR SELF-EMPOWERMENT

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ABSTRACT

Yoga is an ancient discipline designed to bring balance and health to the physical, mental, emotional, and spiritual dimensions of the individual. In the west, yoga is often referred to as a mind-body technique that includes movement and active participation of the body. In the field of complementary and alternative medicine, yogic practices can be categorized as both 'energy medicine' and 'mind-body medicine.' These practices modulate brain activity and diminish the psychological and biological effects of stress. This article tries to explore how yoga education is helpful for making individuals physically fit and inculcate values for self-empowerment.

Keywords: Yoga, Mind, Body, and Medicine

1. INTRODUCTION:

The 21st century is the age of 'science and technology'. It is also known as the age of anxiety and interrogation. There has been immense progress in the field of transportation, communication, space research and IT. Social, moral, political, and economic conditions have undergone momentous changes. The world has shrunk into a global village. Money has become all-important. There is a growing trend towards globalization of trade and economy. The tremendous growth of science and technology has shaken man's faith in values. Loss of spiritual values and emotional capacity has not been compensated by any new set of values. There is cutthroat competition in every field of life. Yoga is discipline that brings about an overall personality development and leaves one feeling confident, energetic, and motivated. It creates the perfect balance in all the systems of the body. It tones the nervous system, releases anxiety, and promotes inner harmony. Yoga strengthens the immune system and helps to develop concentration, focus and mental flexibility. In our daily lives, it helps to develop awareness about the effects of stress and provides the tools to manage it. Its benefits extend from the home and the workplace to every aspect of daily life. Regular practice of yoga is proven to bring improved health in mind and body, higher energy levels and increased productivity. Yoga helps us come out of the vicious circles abundant in our secluded lifestyles. It teaches us to be humble, kind and giving. Most importantly, it not only makes us healthier and fitter, but it also makes us happier and better human beings. Undoubtedly, that is the most vital requirement of our times.

2. YOGA- BOTH MEANS AS WELL AS END

2.1 YOGA AS AN END

Yoga signifies integration of personality at the highest level through control of all modification of mind. Here the meaning is comprehensive and includes all other meanings. It refers to yoga as an end.

2.2 YOGA AS MEANS

To develop such integration, various techniques and practices are employed which got evolved as discipline if yoga passed through stages. Some practices deal with the mind directly and some use indirect means through the body to tackle the mental processes.

3. PRACTICES YOGA CAN BE CLASSIFIED AS:

Asanas: These are special patterns of postures that stabilize mind and body through static stretching. The aim is to establish proper rhythm in neuromuscular tonic impulses and improve general muscle tone.

Pranayama: These practices being control over respiratory impulses which form one of channels of flow of autonomic nerve impulses

Bandhas and Mudras: These are locks and holds of semi voluntary and voluntary muscles in the body. They decongest organs, improve circulation and nutrition by pressure manipulation and contribute to general health and stability.

Kriyas: These are internal purificatory processes that are classified into six divisions. They increase the range of adaptability of tissues forming organs and systems and raise the threshold of their reactivity. They also being control over different reflexes and psycho-physiological balance.

Meditation: It is yogic practice involving control of mental function which starts from initial withdrawal of senses from external objects to complete oblivion of external environment.

Attitude training practices: these are called Yamas and Niyamas. These are self-imposed restrictions at personal and social level to govern one's behavior to form a particular pattern.

4. BENEFITS OF YOGA

- ❖ Yoga helps in the development of holistic personality i.e., physical, mental, and emotional development.
- ❖ Practicing yoga helps in improving the general health.

- ❖ Yoga helps in sorting out psychological problems born out of tensions and conflicts.
- ❖ To attain success in life and to reach a desired goal one must have a cheerful outlook.
- ❖ Yoga helps in the creation of a cheerful outlook.
- ❖ It is further helpful in inculcation of moral values and enhances concentration and memory among students.
- ❖ It develops self-confidence and self-discipline.
- ❖ Working capabilities are increased with the help of yoga.
- ❖ It helps in improving learning efficiency.
- ❖ It is helpful in removing stresses, strain, frustrations, anxiety, and depression.
- ❖ It helps the students to relax during tests and examinations.
- ❖ It controls negative thought waves in the minds.
- ❖ Yoga education is helpful in giving necessary calm to tackle intellectual problems and devoting attention fully.

5. CERTAIN PHYSIOLOGICAL CHANGES ASSOCIATED WITH AGING:

- ❖ Loss of muscle mass and tone decreased muscle to fat ratio.
- ❖ Loss of bone density
- ❖ Loss of flexibility, joint disorders such as arthritis
- ❖ Deterioration of lung elasticity and capacity
- ❖ Disorders of the circulatory system - decreased sensitivity of baroreceptors
- ❖ Degenerative disorders of nervous system - e.g., tremor, Parkinson's disease
- ❖ Sensory and cognitive impairment
- ❖ Psychiatric conditions - depression, anxiety, dementia
- ❖ Reduced immune function.
- ❖ Reduced reserve capacity (slower recovery from exertion, injury, or disease)
- ❖ Sleep disorders
- ❖ Impaired glucose tolerance and insulin sensitivity, strongly linked to abdominal obesity.
- ❖ Further complications can occur as side effects of medication, or medication may mask symptoms of new diseases.

6. REGULAR FITNESS PROGRAMS AND YOGA

Yoga is a unique science and is the most complete approach to a healthy lifestyle. It urges us to explore and challenge our mind, our body, and the very nature of our being. It is the only discipline through which an individual can truly experience inner harmony. The difference between yoga and regular fitness programs lies:

REGULAR FITNESS PROGRAMS	YOGA
Regular fitness programs are goal oriented.	Yoga is a complete process.
Exercise only the physical elements of the body.	Yoga is a discipline that improves the physical, mental, and emotional health of a person.
Focus on completing daily benchmarks.	Focuses on what we are doing and how we feel as we perform the postures.
Fitness programs are competitive in nature.	Yoga sessions are non-competitive and only tap the individual capacity to revitalize the body, mind, and soul.
Concentrate on physical exertion.	Concentrates on physical relaxation
We fail if we do not meet your daily goals.	In Yoga, we succeed by doing it.
Weight training makes you stronger by breaking down and rebuilding muscle tissue, thus it gives a bulky look.	Yoga increases muscle strength is enhanced by toning them.
Fitness programs leave you feeling tired and burnt out.	Yoga sessions leave you feeling rejuvenated and refreshed.

6. YOGA AND MOTIVATION WORKSHOPS:

MOTIVATION AND STRESS-ERADICATION	YOGA
Involves direct but impersonal interaction between the speaker and audience.	Yoga is a direct and personal interaction between the teacher and the student.
Interface between the parties is at an intellectual level.	Interface between the parties is at a spiritual level.
Fails to stimulate the subconscious of the listener.	Stimulates the subconscious of the student.
The spoken word has a limited impact and is forgotten or erased after a brief period.	Yoga evokes the positive energy trapped inside all of us and leaves an everlasting impression on the mind.
Only targets the intellect of the person and does little to bring about an overall development in the listener.	Yoga goes to a much deeper level. It targets the overall personality of the student and helps to attain equilibrium between the mind, body, breath, and spirit.

CONCLUSION

Yoga is a mind-body practice in complementary and alternative medicine not only make an individual feel better but also have an impact on our brain activity, immune function, and endocrine function. At minimum, these practices result in an acute relaxation response, lowering blood pressure, heart rate, and subjective rating of stress. Many medical centers already have incorporated mind-body practices as part of the standard of care. Although these practices are not necessarily prescribed and thought of in the same way as conventional medications, they are being delivered alongside medical treatments to help improve outcomes. As more evidence accumulates, the day will come when mind-body practices are a form of medical treatment provided and prescribed as part of standard medical treatment around the world.

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